

THE HISTORY OF TRANSLATION SCHOOLS IN LITERATURE

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Abstract:

This research paper discusses rich centuries-old history of translation activities. Thanks to translators and translations, different cultures are not isolated from each other, but constantly in contact and in interaction. Thanks to translations, today we know Shakespeare, Goethe, Dante, Aristotle, Plato, Cervantes, translation has formalized the achievements of foreign cultures, which have enriched both Uzbek scientific and everyday culture.

Key words: language, literary translation, translators, cultures of peoples.

Translation activity has rich, centuries-old history, the study of which sheds light on important aspects of the development of language, literature and culture of different peoples.

This article will contribute to the provision of high-quality education for young people, the development of the abilities of talented young people, the formation of creative, socially active, spiritually rich individuals, and the training of highly qualified and competitive personnel.

In Europe, monks in monasteries made the first translations. They translated literature of religious content. In the Monzei monastery in 748, the Gospel of Matthew was translated (only a few fragments have reached us) and one of the sermons of Blessed Augustine was translated.

By the 10th century, the monk Notker founded a school at the monastery of St. Gallen. Notker was engaged in translating philosophical, theological and natural scientific works of late antiquity and the early Middle Ages and writing commentaries on them. He translated Aristotle's Rhetoric and Categories, Boethius' Consolation of Philosophy, and Bucolics Virgil. He created many new words to convey concepts that were previously absent from the language.

By the 12th century, Spain became a true translation center in Europe. Archbishop Don Raimundo founded a translation school in Toledo in 1126. Philosophical, medical, mathematical treatises, works on astronomy and astrology were translated into Latin from Arabic and ancient Greek. The translation school in Toledo existed for about 200 years. 52 manuscripts with hundreds of translations are kept in the Toledo Cathedral and the National Library.

library in Madrid.

The first literary artistic translations appeared in Europe in the 12th-13th centuries - adaptations of the Song of Roland, a verse novel about Alexander the Great. For example, in 1133, the cleric Conrad of Regensburg translated the Song of Roland from French into German. One of the greatest poets of the chivalric genre, Hartmann von Aue, translated and freely adapted the verse novels of Chretien de Troyes, Yvain and Erec. The first translations of artistic texts were of an adapted nature, translators sometimes modified the texts so much that they sometimes turned into independent works. For centuries, there was a discussion regarding the translation process. Some translators demanded a complete, literal correspondence between the original and translated texts, while others advocated for the "spirit" of the work, defending the position of a free translation. The number of translations significantly increases in Europe after the foundation of universities. With the development of sciences, the range of translation also expands: philosophical treatises, texts on astronomy, alchemy, and medicine are translated. During the Renaissance in Europe interest in ancient authors and their works is emerging. Ancient texts in first place among translated books in the 14th century (they are popular in France, Spain, England, Italy). But this historical period did not give big names among translators, many translations are carried out, as a rule, anonymously.

In the 15th century, individual translators advocated translation that conveyed the original in meaning and at the same time observed the norms of the native language, for example, in Germany – Heinrich Steinhöfel (translator of Aesop and Boccaccio), in France – Joachim du Bellay (translator of Ovid) and Etienne Dolet (Plato). This is how the tradition of cultural adaptation was born. For example, the 15th century German

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translator Albrecht von Eyb, when translating Plautus' comedies, not only replaced the setting of the action with German, but also changed the names of the characters.

In conclusion, it can be said that at present the study of the history of translation activities and translation teachings is rightly considered as one of the most important areas of research. Evidence of the strengthening of the legal and social status of translation can be seen in the fact that in 1991 the FIT established World Translation Day. It falls on September 30 and is associated with the name of St. Jerome (September 30, 420), a famous writer, historian and translator, author of the famous translation of the Holy Scriptures from Hebrew into Latin.

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